

Studies on Driver's Response with Peripheral Moving Targets under Different Road Lighting Situations- A Realistic Approach

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Abstract: A field investigation on road lighting was carried out, to integrate extended findings of the mesopic luminance area involving visual performance of the road users, under different light sources with varied spectrums within a driving environment. The vision related to night-time lies in the mesopic region where both rods and cones cells of human eye contribute to visual performance. The mesopic luminance region comes between the photopic and scotopic luminance region. The entire research work consists of a real time survey, based on the measurement of reaction time (the time duration between the moment of starting the car and pressing brake after observing the obstruction) of drivers of different ages and genders under different lighting situations with different driving experiences of various Indian roads. It is found in the study that the braking reaction time is changing with luminance value as well as illuminance value of the road but it is more precisely changing with respect to the spectral power distribution of the light source used in the road lighting design. The color property of the source has also a significant effect on the object detection also.

Keywords — Object Detection, Reaction Time of Driver, High Pressure Sodium Vapor Lamp, Metal-halide Lamp, Ceramic Discharge Lamp, LED, Road Lighting.

INTRODUCTION

All road lighting should provide safety and comfort to all road users. The drivers' requirements are most important when designing lighting recommendations and designing the lighting of roads where vehicular traffic is dominant. Road lights should provide good visibility condition and reduce potential hazards of accidents. Well-designed road lighting should permit users of road at night to move with the greatest possible safety and comfort so that the traffic capacity of the road at night is as much equal as possible with the daytime. Efficiently designed road lighting enables the driver to see distinctly without the use of dipped or driving headlights and helps to locate any traffic signs and possible obstacles on the road without difficulty. It also

helps pedestrian to see distinctly the edges of the footways, vehicles and obstacles. The conventional system of photometry [1] relies strictly on the photopic luminous efficiency function (V_λ) to represent the light output (in lumens) from all electric light sources, irrespective of their intended application. V_λ is based upon the spectral sensitivity of foveal (long- and middle-wavelength sensitive) cones of human eye, peaking at 555 nm, which takes place at high ambient light levels, e.g. during the daytime. It is a very useful function to transform the spectral power distribution (SPD) of any light source into a single measure of light output (luminous flux and luminous intensity) or light level (luminance and illuminance). At very low light levels where both cones and rods of human eye participate in the visual response, as they do in the visual periphery for many night-time applications, V_λ is obviously not a completely satisfactory rectifying transform for SPD. Under these night-time applications the effectiveness of lamps with relatively more short wavelength radiation can be underestimated because the peak of the spectral response for rods, represented by the scotopic luminous efficiency function (V'_λ), is approximately 507 nm. Proper characterization of light source output and light level is particularly important in night-time applications because under low light levels the significance of target size and contrast for visual performance is much greater than it is under high light levels [2–5]. Mesopic vision relates to lighting levels between photopic and scotopic vision. The mesopic spectral sensitivity is not constant. It shifts from photopic to scotopic with decreasing light levels. The mesopic spectral sensitivity was defined by the CIE technical report on “Recommended System for Mesopic Photometry Based on Visual Performance”, 2010 [6]. According to this new CIE report mesopic photometric system is valid between 0.005cd/m² and 5cd/m². Road lighting recommendations fall within the mesopic region where both rods and cones of human eye contribute to visual performance. It can also be argued that the social consequences of proper characterization of light at night are particularly important to safety and security as well as to energy utilization, light trespass and light pollution.

In the last decade increased attention has been given to this topic [7]. Among the early examples of this increased interest were the studies of He et al., which helped to establish the basis for a proposed unified system of photometry, bridging the conventional photopic and scotopic luminous efficiency functions through the mesopic region [5]. Although a unified system of photometry is essential for providing a quantitative method for characterizing any light SPD at any light level, it was also important to begin to better understand visual performance under low light levels used in night-time applications. Additional laboratory studies, static field studies and a dynamic field study of driving extended the fundamental findings of these early laboratory studies to more realistic contexts. These more practical studies corroborated the basic findings from the laboratory, but they dramatically showed that SPD can have an even more pronounced effect on visual performance relying on the peripheral retina than would be predicted from unified photometry alone because of the very large interactions between stimulus variables such as target contrast and size. In effect then, mischaracterization of the luminous flux generated by a light source at low light levels can be greatly magnified in a practical context where moving small targets of low contrast must be seen by using peripheral vision [8 - 11]. Unlike small errors in characterizing light under office conditions, small errors in characterizing light under roadway conditions can make the difference between seeing and not seeing a target. This present field study adopted a similar protocol to that used by Akashi and Rea, in which subjects were asked to detect off-axis (away from the road axis) flashing targets while driving along a street [12-15]. In the present study, subjects were required to perform a more difficult target identification task, utilizing higher-order decision making than simply responding to the onset of a flashed target. Here, subjects were asked to identify off-axis target movements from the street, and to respond by braking a car, respectively, while driving along a street at a constant speed of 20kmph. Four sets of light sources were used at night, a set of High-Pressure sodium vapour (HPSV-SON), a set of metal halide (MHL) ‘white’ light sources, a set of Ceramic Discharge Metal Halide (CDM-TT) and a set of LED light sources; all sets were installed in three luminaires producing nearly identical light distributions on the roadway [12 - 14]. In addition; the same task was performed during the day-time. The overall aim of this paper is to analyze the real time responses of drivers while reaching towards any object or object detection under different light sources.

EXPERIMENT PROTOCOL

The experiment was designed to simulate a realistic scenario where the driver of a car must decide a course of action based upon detection. The driver was requested to respond clearly and deliberately to the perceived movement of a target coming toward

the street by braking.

The experimental setup for the assessment of driver's reaction time consists of an Ultrasound motion sensor, five sequentially activated detection targets, a PIC microcontroller with relay assembly for controlling the detection targets, a precision time counter and its activation circuit. Fig. 1 shows the layout of the experimental system. There were five detection targets, set side-by-side (designated, left to right from the driver's perspective, A, B, C, D, E in Fig. 2) on a frame-stand on the edge of the street pavement. The flip discs were 1.45m above the pavement surface. From the driver's position when the flip dots were activated, the central target was 6.03m to the right of the axis of the road. The five targets consisted of a 1 mm thick 'flip disc'. All flip discs were painted black. But in the front of the disks 1/8th portion was covered by a white colored fluorescent paper. When all of the discs were flipped to the white position, it was seen as a square target from the driver's viewing distance; the measured reflectance of the square target is 0.4. Each flip discs were 221mm wide and high. Five discs were mounted on a black frame (1148mm wide and 261mm high with); the electrical control circuitry for the target was located behind the frame. The flip-dot targets and time counter were activated when the wheels of the car interrupted an Ultrasound motion beam across the road pavement. The flip-dot targets were located 28.4m from the starting point of the car. A pre-programmed sequence determined whether the flip-dot sequence would simulate movement of a target toward or away from the street. Upon activation, three of the five-disc targets were flipped sequentially, either from the centre target toward the street (in order, C, B, A) or from the centre target away from the street (in order, C, D, E) such that a single moving target appeared in the driver's peripheral visual field (Fig. 3). When the driver recognizes flip disc rotation pattern, he then sends a stop signal via a FM remote to the time counter, recording the reaction time for the detection.

Fig. 1: Experimental Set-up with all Circuitry

Fig. 2: Sequentially Activated Targets

Fig. 3: Detection targets simulating movement towards the street (i.e. CàBàA)

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

12 subjects aged from 23 to 45 years participated in this night time experiment every night, each subject taking turns to drive the same car along the test route. Prior to driving, experimenter gave the subjects instructions on the experimental procedures. Subjects were instructed to (1) drive along the straight portion of the street at a constant speed of 20kmph; (2) look at the detection target; and (3) respond to the apparent direction of target movement, toward the street, by braking the car. Approximately 10 min were required for each subject to complete the response analysis for a given lighting condition. After completing the response analysis with all 12 subjects, the lighting condition was changed. On a separate day the experimenter changed the lighting condition, which required approximately 30 min to complete. For all the 12 subjects, approximately 3hrs were needed to gather data for all-in-one lighting conditions in one night. While driving, subjects used low-beam headlamps (55W), conforming to Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) standards. The illuminance provided on the central target by the headlamps were 1.21 lx when the car was parked at the target initiation point. Table. 1 shows the horizontal photopic illuminance and luminance under experimental lighting conditions. Fig. 4 depicts the actual experimental set-up of the study. Actual pictorial representation of Flip dot disk stimulus and Ultra-sound motion sensor is given in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6.

Fig. 4: Actual Experimental Set-up

Fig. 5: Flip Dot Disk Stimulus

Fig. 6: Ultra-Sound Motion Sensor

Table I. Horizontal photopic illuminance and luminance under experimental lighting conditions

Sl.no	Lighting Condition	Average Illuminance (Lux)		Standard Deviation (Lux)		Photopic Luminance (cd/m ²)	
		Driver's Lane	Area	Driver's Lane	Area	Driver's Lane	Area
1	HPSV(SON)	15.99	13.38	9.26	8.57	0.84	
2	MHL	25.36	20.63	24.39	21.14	1.2	
3	CDM-TT	28.37	24.93	7.22	8.26	1.42	
4	LED	31.4	32.97	12.49	14.04	1.57	

EXPERIMENTAL RESULT

Reaction times were estimated as the difference between the time when the car's front wheel cut the ultrasound waves, giving a 5V dc pulse to PIC microcontroller to start the sequence movement of the detection targets and the driver recognizing the complete pattern of the detection targets with instantly stopping the car. However, the data were completely unambiguous as to when a subject reacted to a target presentation. The subjects correctly braked in response to simulated target movement. The experimental results are shown below.

Drivers Reaction time analysis on the street under 70W High Pressure Sodium Vapor Lamp (SON-T):

The above mentioned experimental street illuminated with 3 street lighting luminaire (Philips catalog name SRX066) with 70W High Pressure Sodium Vapor lamp mounted on a 5m high adjustable laboratory developed pole with 1m bracket length, 00 tilt. All the drivers, i.e., the subjects used to drive a Hyundai EON car, with an average speed of 20kmph. The target object has

been controlled the sensing and control circuit already mentioned. The 12 subjects individually recognize the target in different time. The response time is given in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7: Reaction times under High Pressure Sodium Vapor Lamp

Drivers Reaction time analysis on the street under 70W Metal Halide lamp (MHL):

The above mentioned experimental street illuminated with 3 road lighting luminaire (Philips catalog name SRX066) with 70W Metal Halide lamp mounted on a 5m high adjustable laboratory developed pole with 1m bracket length, 00 tilt. All the drivers, i.e., the subjects used to drive a Hyundai EON car, with an average speed of 20kmph. The target object has been controlled the sensing and control circuit already mentioned. The 12 subjects individually recognize the target in different time. The response time is given in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8: Reaction times under Metal Halide Lamp

Drivers Reaction time analysis on the street under 70W Ceramic Discharge Metal Halide lamp (CDM-TT)

The above mentioned experimental street illuminated with 3 road lighting luminaire (Philips catalog name CELSTE SGP301) with 70W Ceramic Discharge Metal Halide lamp (CDM-TT) mounted on a 5m high adjustable laboratory developed pole with 1m bracket length, 00 tilt. All the drivers, i.e., the subjects used to drive a Hyundai EON car, with an average speed of 20kmph. The target object has been controlled the sensing and control circuit already mentioned. The 12 subjects individually recognize the target in different time. The response time is given in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9: Reaction times under Ceramic Discharge Metal Halide Lamp

Drivers Reaction time analysis on the street under 45W LED luminaire:

The above mentioned experimental street illuminated with 3 road lighting luminaire (Philips catalog name BRP320) with 45W LED luminaire mounted on a 5m high adjustable laboratory developed pole with 1m bracket length, 00 tilt. All the drivers, i.e., the subjects used to drive a Hyundai EON car, with an average speed of 20kmph. The target object has been controlled the sensing and control circuit already mentioned. The 12 subjects individually recognize the target in different time. The response time is given in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10: Reaction times under LED Lamp

Overall reaction times of the 12 subjects under different street lighting luminaires are tabulated in Table. 2
 Table II. Reaction times of drivers under different lighting condition

Mean Reaction Time of Drivers under Different Lighting Condition:

Graph in Fig. 11 shows mean reaction times for correctly braking in response to simulated target movement under 4 lighting conditions (SON, MHL, CDM-TT, LED); only correct responses to simulated target movements were used in these figures and in the statistical analyses. From the graph, it is evident that the mean response time of drivers was quickest under 70W CDM-TT lamp with 1.51sec. The mean response under 45W LED luminaire was near about the response of CDM-TT with 1.55sec. The highest response time achieved under 70W SON-T lamp, 1.88sec. From the graph it can be concluded that the response time of the drivers decreased monotonically as the photopic illuminance and luminance increase.

Fig. 11: Mean Reaction times of Drivers under different lighting conditions

Day Time Experiment:

Correct reaction times of drivers were also obtained during day-time hours when the lighting conditions were highest and drivers should have been able to respond to a target most quickly, to better gauge the difference in response times between SON, MHL, CDM-TT and LED found in the night-time experiment. The day-time experiment took place at the same location as the night-time experiment, from 15:00 to 16:30. The sky was partially cloudy in the morning and became cloudy in the afternoon. The sun set at 17.46. Recorded Reaction times are given in Fig. 12.

Fig. 12: Day-time reaction times of the Drivers

Mean Reaction Times with Standard Errors for Braking Under the Four Night-Time Lighting Conditions (SON-T, MH, CDM-TT and LED) and During the Day (DAY):

Graphical representation in Fig. 13 shows the correct response times for the day-time experiment (DAY) compared to those for the four lighting conditions in the night-time experiment (HPSV (SON-T), MHL, CDM-TT and LED). The results showed that the correct response times during the DAY were significantly shorter than those under any of the night-time lighting conditions.

Fig. 13: Mean Reaction times with day-time response

Luminaire Parameter

Parameter	Luminaires Used		
Luminaire Type	Road lighting luminaire suitable for use with High Pressure Sodium Vapour SON/SON-T70W (I or E) lamp.(Philips catalogue name SRX 066)	Compact and sturdy low wattage street lighting luminaire suitable for use with tubular high pressure Sodium Vapour lamps SON-T 70W (E / I). The luminaire can also be used with CDM-TT 70W ceramic discharge Metal Halide lamps. (Philips catalogue name CELESTE SGP 301)	Philips Green Line Green line Consuming 45w (including driver) Green Line features latest LEDs and delivers consistent light output, stable color performance and high color rendering.(Philips catalogue name BRP 320)
Figure			

Parameter	Luminaires Used		
For Lamp	1*70w SON-T 1*70w SON-E 1*70w MHL	1*70w CDM-TT	24 High Power LED
Lamp operating voltage(V)	230	230	230
IP	 65		
Polar plot	SRX 066	SGP 301	BRP 320

CONCLUSION

Correct reaction times were significantly shorter for the CDM-TT and LED than for the SON and MH at the same photopic light level. Though the average illuminance of MH and CDM-TT were close to each other but there is a significant difference in their time response. This conclusion is illustrated in Fig. 14. It is evident from the graph that driver’s reaction time decreases with increase in illuminance on the road surface. As expected, the correct reation times were shorter in the day-time experiment than for any of the night-time lighting conditions. Average of driver’s response time under daylight was 1.41sec, which is much less than the other four lighting conditions under night time experiment. Fig. 14 shows the comparison of drivers’ response time on the street under different lighting situations. The driver response time under 70W CDM-TT was the quickest among all the four different lighting conditions at night time. Though luminance and illuminance for 45W LED was better than 70W CDM-TT (Table. 1), but the reaction time was better under 70W CDM-TT due to the color appearance. The results of the entire experimental study depict that the braking response time is changing with luminance value as well as illuminance value of the road but it is more precisely changing with respect to the spectral power distribution of the light source used in the road lighting design. The color property of the source has also a significant effect on the object detection also.

Fig. 14. Comparison of Drivers’ Reaction Time

FUTURE SCOPE

In future this research work can further be extended with some real-life conditions. As the light source used in the street contributes to object detection on a road, hence the light source matches with the night time vision (mesopic) can also be considered. A better approach of sensing drivers' response should also be taken care of. Finally, the drivers' response should be analysed under realistic visual challenged situation. It can be done in three ways:

- Driver Response Measurement under Mesopic Light Sources.
- Driver Response Measurement by Advanced sensing method like Electroencephalography (EEG test).
- Driver Response Measurement under Visually Challenged Situation- under Rain and under Foggy Condition.

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